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ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND DEVELOPMENT OPPORTUNITIES OF HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY ON THE EXAMPLE OF SERGIIVKA RESORT (UKRAINE)

The object of research is the hospitality industry in the context of the recovery of the industry and the fight against the effects of the pandemic. The development of domestic tourism and local destinations is considered one of the most effective ways to restore the industry. At the same time, experts recommended that the greatest attention be paid to health tourism and ecotourism. The analysis of the potential of the institutions of the sanatorium-resort direction and the study of the problems of the development of the sphere of hospitality were considered on the example of the resort of Sergiivka, Odessa region of Ukraine.

In the course of the study of the state of the resort base of the region, methods of comparative analysis, generalization and systematization of information about the natural-climatic, social and other resources of the region, the state of hospitality institutions and sanatorium-resort complexes were used. Strengths and challenges were identified that hinder their effective use. So, Sergiivka is considered one of the largest seaside resorts in the region, which is located in the beach area and has a good climate, environmental friendliness and significant balneological resources. However, the problematic issues are the underdeveloped infrastructure of the resort, the level of service that requires improvement, the quality of the room stock, the work of restaurants and the organization of recreation.

The studies carried out indicate the importance of developing measures for the reconstruction of most powerful establishments of the hotel and restaurant and sanatorium business. The need to create comfortable living conditions in accordance with world standards, to improve the range and quality of services, in particular, to organize leisure for adults and children, was noted. One of the recommended directions is to expand the range of services in the SPA and Wellness directions, which will allow more efficient use of the healing, restorative and health-improving resources of the balneological resort. Organic production and ecotransformation are also considered priority innovative areas of development. It is promising to use the agro-industrial potential of the region for the production of organic, environmentally friendly food products from local raw materials, as well as the introduction of more environmentally friendly and resource-efficient technologies.

Keywords: hospitality industry, hotel and restaurant business, Sergiivka resort, analysis of hospitality establishments, health resort business.

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1. Introduction

The hospitality industry is a special sector of the economy, it consists of a group of industries and enterprises, subjects of tourism, hotel, restaurant business, whose tasks are aimed at meeting the demand for various types of accommodation, food, recreation, entertainment, transportation, and the like. This is a diversified, dynamic sector of the economy, which, under favorable conditions, is able to show high growth rates, to give impetus to the development of a number of

related industries (agriculture, energy, transport, etc.). Accordingly, the development of the hospitality industry, hotel and restaurant, tourism business contributes to attracting investment, socio-cultural and economic development at the local, regional and state levels [1–3].

But the realities of recent years, when humanity met with the coronavirus pandemic, the closure of borders, recommendations to avoid mass events, etc., also showed the vulnerability of the hospitality and tourism industry as a whole, as well as individual market players. Tourist,

hotel, restaurant business all over the world has met with a mass of problems, has undergone a radical transformation of views on effective forms of organizing the work of institutions and models of their development. In each country for 2019–2020 a significant part of restaurants closed, demand and production volumes decreased, and hospitality revenues fell. The task of «staying afloat» came to the fore, the search for new mechanisms that would ensure the preservation of the viability of the hotel, restaurant, tourism industry and allow to quickly adapt to the new dynamic conditions of the business environment [4–6].

Due to the pandemic, there have been changes in the organization of the hospitality industry. Thus, the development of domestic tourism is considered by the experts of the World Tourism Organization as one of the most effective ways to restore the industry. Among local destinations, it is recommended to pay the most attention to health tourism and ecotourism related to nature and outdoor activities [7].

Thus, *the object of research* is the hospitality industry in the context of the recovery of the industry and the fight against the effects of the pandemic. *The aim of research* is to analyze the potential and problems of the development of the hospitality sector on the example of the South of the Odesa region (Ukraine), in particular the resort of Sergiivka.

2. Methods of research

The following scientific methods were used in the work:

- method of generalization and systematization (when studying literary sources on the research topic);
- comparative analysis (in the study of the state of the resort base of the region);
- SWOT analysis (summarizing the strengths and weaknesses of the Sergiivka resort in terms of the state and development of the hospitality industry).

3. Research results and discussion

Sergiivka is a resort located on the coast of the Shabolatsky estuary in the Bilhorod-Dnistrovsky district of the Odesa region of Ukraine. A narrow sand bar, which is used as a beach, separates it from the Black Sea [8]. The peculiarities of recreation in Sergiivka are determined by the special status of this area – this is the most seaside balneological resort in the Odessa region. The peculiarities of recreation in Sergiivka are determined by the special status of this area – this is the most seaside balneological resort in the Odessa region. An important healing factor is the water of the Shabolatsky estuary, which has been used for medicinal purposes for a long time. In terms of physical and chemical properties, the therapeutic mud of the Shabolatsky estuary is not only not inferior, but also surpasses in many respects the therapeutic mud of other resorts [9, 10].

The climate of the Sergiivka resort is moderately continental and relatively dry. The duration of the warm season is from April to October. The number of sunny days per year exceeds 290. In addition, Sergiivka pleases with cleaner beaches, lower prices, fewer people compared to Odessa beaches and the Zatoka. The residential area includes high-rise buildings with a large number of coniferous and deciduous trees, landscaped park areas. At the end of the last century, many boarding houses, children's camps, sanatoriums, etc. were built in Sergiivka [8, 11].

Many favorable natural factors provide opportunities for full recovery. For medical purposes, the brine of the Shabolatsky estuary (mineral baths) is used, for the treatment of internal organs, waters from wells (analogs of Myrhorod ones) are used, large reserves of silt therapeutic mud, which is unique in its properties and is popular in health resorts throughout Ukraine. The sanatoriums of Sergiivka successfully use natural factors in medical practice. Treatment of the musculoskeletal system, digestive and respiratory organs, diseases of the nervous system, gynecological and dermatological diseases are the main profiles of the Sergiivka sanatoriums [10, 12].

All this leads to an increase every year in popularity not only among people seeking to improve their health, but also among tourists and people who prefer rest by the sea. So, at present in Sergiivka only during the summer period of the year, according to statistical data, more than 25,000 people have a rest. During the pandemic, the number of tourists in the region only increased.

But the ecological purity of the region is under threat. There are often warnings about the possibility of a technogenic and ecological disaster in the resort areas of Sergiivka and the Zatoka, where there is a problem with drinking water, urgent modernization and reconstruction of treatment facilities for their catastrophic state and high technogenic load on the environment [13]. Also, rest in Sergiivka can be overshadowed by the fact that the infrastructure of the resort is not developed, the level of service requires constant improvement. The Sergiivka resort was designed and actively built in the 70–80s of the last century. In the 90s, it was partially abandoned. Some buildings are abandoned and slowly collapsing, in some places Sergiivka resembles the abandoned city of Pripjat and makes a depressing impression. The infrastructure of catering and recreation services requires improvement and reorganization [14].

Sergiivka resort is located on the territory of Bessarabia, which is also called Budzhak and Danube. This is a kind of island, connected to the «mainland» by only two bridges – across the Dniester estuary near the Gulf and across the Dniester, which has become a cozy home for hundreds of thousands of residents of different nationalities. This is a unique laboratory for culturally rich recreation, excursion and educational visits. Traditions of different peoples and eras met here. The medieval fortress Bilhorod-Dnistrovsk is here adjacent to the modernized guilty production of the once Swiss village of Shabo. On the other hand, the legendary Izmail and Kiliia were once impregnable fortresses, now peaceful ports on the Danube, ecological reserves. In the place where the large European river Danube flows into the Black Sea is the city of Vilково – «Ukrainian Venice». Mosaic of Ukrainian, Bulgarians, Moldavians, Germans, Old Believers, Jews, Gagauz, Greeks and other nationalities and peoples living in Bessarabia, provided the uniqueness of the region, manifested in culture, structure, names of settlements. These are Greek Tira, Ukrainian Cossack Belolesye, Division, Turkish Tuzla, Hadjider, German Sarata, Tarutino, Bulgarian Bolgrad, Kulevcha, etc. [15].

However, today, with the high potential of the region, Bessarabia remains a depressed territory. Low incomes of the population, problems with employment, sale of land, environmental problems, primarily related to access and quality of water, waste processing, problems with information security, interethnic relations and many other problems are of concern to the inhabitants of Bessarabia today [16, 17].

It is the development of tourism, the sphere of the hotel and restaurant business that is extremely relevant. This can become an impetus for the development of all other areas of management, resolve the issue of improper use of resources, and improve the quality of life of the inhabitants of Bessarabia.

Resort base of the urban-type settlement Sergiivka is represented by a fairly large number of hotel enterprises (Table 1), which indicates high competition and the need to constantly update the material base, improve the conditions for guests' recreation, both the quality of accommodation and food, leisure activities, and the like.

Common to these enterprises of the hotel and restaurant industry is a medical and recreational profile, construction and start of work almost 30–40 years ago, a rather low level of comfort in rooms, catering in canteens, the problem of spending free time and leisure, except for rest by the sea.

Catering establishments are represented mainly by canteens at sanatoriums, hotels and small bars.

According to the analysis of the reviews of vacationers and guests of Sergiivka, they received unforgettable impressions of the climate, sea, other natural features of the region, the presence of a large number of fresh vegetables, fruits, berries, and the multinational flavor of the region. At the same time, it was noted that it is advisable to improve the work of restaurants, the organization of recreation and the quality of the number of rooms. The main requirements of the guests of Sergiivka are sufficient comfort of living conditions for families and individually, there is a request for SPA and Wellness services. Meals should be varied, from fresh local raw materials (seasonal fruits, vegetables, dairy products, etc.), taking into account the special needs of children, youth, the elderly, and a health-improving orientation.

Table 1

Analysis of hospitality establishments in Sergiivka

Name of company	Volume	Nutrition	Service characteristics	Note
«Play» hotel	9-storey, 4*, 224 rooms, 324 beds: of which apartments, suites, junior suites, double and single; single and double rooms of the 1st category; 2-bed rooms of the II category	Restaurant for 365 seats (2nd floor), cafe 40 seats with a summer veranda for 40 seats (1st floor)	Summer vacation, conference room	Started work in 1988, park area
«South» hotel	16-storey building, 1, 2, 3-bed rooms, suite (150 rooms)	Cafe	Accommodation, recreation, sports ground, conference hall	Under reconstruction
Sanatorium named after S. Lazo	7-storey building, 250 rooms (rooms 1-, 2-bed, junior suite with balconies) for 500 visitors	Dining room, 5 meals a day	Treatment, rehabilitation, rest	Started work in 1984
«Patria» sanatorium	480 beds, 146 rooms, 2*	Dining room, 5 meals a day	Treatment, rehabilitation, relaxation by the sea, beach fitness	Reconstruction 2013, park zone $S_2=4$ hectares
«Golden Field» sanatorium	500 places, 244 rooms 2*, 9 rooms – 3*	Dining room, 5 meals a day	Rehabilitation, rest by the sea, disco, park area	Started work in 1980, park zone $S_2=6.3$ hectares
«Horizon» sanatorium	2 five-storey buildings (1-, 2-, 3-bed rooms and a suite)	Dining room, 5 meals a day	Treatment, relaxation, gym	Park zone $S_2=6.5$ hectares
Victoria Rehabilitation Center	500 beds, 320 rooms, 9-storey building, 3*	Canteen	Treatment, rest	Started work in 1974
«Senataty» sanatorium (from the Moldavian «Health»)	400 people	Dining room, 5 meals a day	Rest, health improvement	–
LLC Medical and Health Complex «Lyman»	Lux, 2, 3, 4-bed rooms in comfortable sleeping buildings	Bar-restaurant	Rest, health improvement	Started in 2005 and 2007
«Coral Reef» recreation center	3-storey cottage-type buildings for 100 guests	Absent	Spa vacation	–
«Cote d'Azur» recreation center	5 cozy 2-storey cottages, suite, junior suite, 2-, 3-bed rooms	Absent	Spa vacation	–
«Petrel» recreation center	2-storey cottages for 15 people, 4–7 people	Absent	Resort rest, billiards	–
«Parus» recreation center	Up to 40 seats	Dining room, 3 meals a day	Rest, diagnostics, health improvement	–
«Sorceress» recreation center	Three 4-storey buildings with 2-, 3-bed rooms	«Sea» cafe	Resort rest, children's rest, billiards	–
«Seagull» boarding house	4 wooden and stone buildings with 1-, 2-, 3-bed rooms	Dining room with the possibility of 5 meals a day	Resort rest, billiards	–
«Sunny Beach» pension	400 beds, rooms specialized for families with children, 2, 3, 4-bed rooms	3, 4, 5 meals a day with waiter service	Children's town «Gulliver» with attractions, sports grounds, dance floor	–
Health-improving sports base «Medic-2»	For organized groups of children in 5-storey buildings in 2, 3, 4-bed rooms, suite	3 meals a day	Parking, first-aid post, sports and playground, library, disco	–

Note: based on data from [18]

The conducted studies of the hospitality industry in Sergiivka are systematized in Table 2, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of development are revealed.

The studies carried out indicate the need and prospects for the development of measures for the reconstruction of most powerful establishments of the hotel and restaurant and sanatorium-resort business, improving work in compliance with such innovative development directions:

1. Creation of comfortable living conditions that meet the requirements of regulatory documents and international standards:

1.1. Rational organization of the functioning of hotel services and the provision of quality services.

1.2. Equipping rooms with the necessary furniture, equipment and connection to the Internet network, cable TV, communications.

1.3. Creation of conditions for vacationers, as well as business people (to reduce the negative impact of the seasonal factor) for comfortable living, completing visiting tasks, having a job.

1.4. Equipping conference rooms with modern equipment for various events throughout the year.

1.5. Organization of parking and improvement of conditions for storing cars.

1.6. Use, rental of eco-vehicles (electric cars, bicycles, etc.).

2. Improving the work of restaurant enterprises:

2.1. Development of a menu with the inclusion of exquisite and simple dishes of national, local and European cuisine, a healthy food menu, a specialized menu. Today Bessarabia is inhabited by almost 140 nationalities and ethnic groups, they are carriers of their original ethnic culture, traditions and unique national cuisine.

2.2. Organization of high quality service and comfortable conditions.

2.3. Use of innovative technological equipment.

2.4. Purchase and use of local raw materials. One of the priority areas of development is agriculture, since organic production of environmentally friendly products is popular in the world, especially local ones, which are distinguished by safety, higher nutritional value and safety due to the lack of long-term storage and transportation [19, 20]. Also, in particular, the Development Strategy of the Odessa region named organic production and eco-transformation [21]. One of the main natural resources of Odessa is its land resources. Together with the geographical position and favorable climate, this makes it possible to offer a wide range of local cereals, legumes, fruits, vegetables, berries, grapes, greens, including medicinal and aromatic raw materials and, as a result, beekeeping products. The region's potential is high enough for the development of animal husbandry (pig breeding, cattle breeding, sheep breeding, poultry breeding), processing (flour-grinding, dairy, wine-making, etc.) industries both on an industrial scale and in a small, craft format. In addition, the Odessa region has access to the Black Sea, large estuaries, two large rivers flow through its territory – the Dniester and the Danube, indicates the availability of sea and river fish, and seafood, including endemic Black Sea gobies, kalkan, glossa, tulka, mullet, Danube herring.

2.5. Effective quality control management and food safety guarantee.

3. Expansion of the range of services, primarily due to the SPA and Wellness directions, as well as the organization of leisure for adults and children.

Table 2

SWOT analysis of the Sergiivka resort in the aspect of the state and development of the hospitality industry

Strengths	Weaknesses
I. Geographical location, natural resource potential and state of the environment (external)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – favorable geographical location in a climatic resort area on the Black Sea coast (800 m to the coastline); – proximity to the Shabolatsky estuary, the water and mud of which have medicinal properties; – significant health-improving and recreational potential (sea, curative mud, mineral springs, a wide range of fresh vegetables, fruits, livestock products, beekeeping, winemaking). Sergiivka is one of the most environmentally friendly resorts with a high coefficient of landscaping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – distance from large cities and highways, railway station: to Odessa – 70 km; Romania-Izmail-Odessa highway – 8 km; to the railway station – 25 km; – poor condition of roads; – pronounced seasonality of the resort period and, accordingly, the occupancy of the hotel and rooms
II. Economic and labor potential (external)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – high agro-industrial potential; – high educational level of the population, the availability of medical, pedagogical specialists, experienced restaurant workers, the possibility of attracting them to work in the hospitality industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – lack of highly qualified specialists with knowledge of the modern features of organizing the work of tourism, hotel, restaurant enterprises, design and landscape of hotel and restaurant complexes and territories, marketing and advertising, computer technologies, etc.
III. Infrastructure development (external)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – significant recreational and balneological resources, the presence of sea air, mineral water, water from the Black Sea, Shabolatsky estuary and mud; – historical and cultural heritage of the region, a high concentration of archaeological sites, including the ancient era 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – unsatisfactory state of infrastructure, first of all, motor roads; – insufficient number of places to stay in comfortable hotels and food in restaurants; – significant scattering of monuments of history, culture and religion across the territory of the region; – undeveloped information space about the tourism opportunities of the region and separately the hotels; – high competition; – economic crisis, coronavirus pandemic; – growth in utility bills; – need to modernize most of the rooms, water supply networks, sewerage systems, electricity supply; – not entirely effective advertising; – influence of the seasonal factor on the number of rooms and profits; – lack of services for organizing recreation for adults

4. The implementation of more environmentally friendly and resource-efficient technologies in the activities of hospitality institutions, in accordance with global trends [22–24]. Sergiivka has a high potential in terms of the use of non-traditional types of energy: wind energy (wind generators), solar energy (solar energy, installation of solar panels, modules on the roofs), biomass energy (processed products of straw, sunflower, etc.). Since the region has an overwhelming majority of sunny days and an almost constant wind with an average annual speed of more than 5 m/s, and the above crops are grown in large volumes, all this makes it extremely promising. Thirdly, the cultivation of flax in Ukraine, its processing, the availability of natural textiles allows the use of 100 % organic cotton linen, curtains, bedspreads and other interior elements from natural fabrics. Fourthly, due to the presence of forests, practical experience and woodworking craftsmen, it is possible to manufacture and install wooden furniture, interior decoration. In addition, eco-establishments should be characterized by environmental sustainability and preservation of the environment. All this is possible provided that an environmental training program is provided, local culture is taken into account, economic returns to the local community are ensured, etc.

The use of such innovative strategies for the development of hospitality enterprises in modern conditions allows them to increase their competitiveness, especially in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences. However, their implementation largely depends on the potential of the region, the availability of cooperation with enterprises in other industries, support both at the local and state levels.

4. Conclusions

As a result of the analysis of the potential and problems of the development of the hospitality sphere in the South of the Odessa region, in particular, the resort of Sergiivka, a high climatic, historical, cultural, economic and labor potential of the region was established for the development of tourism and related industries. An assessment of the activities of institutions of the hotel and restaurant business and sanatorium-resort complexes was carried out, the importance of improving their work in a number of areas was established, first of all:

- creating comfortable living conditions in accordance with international standards;
- improvement of the range and quality of services of restaurant business institutions;
- increasing the use of the potential of agriculture, the processing industry of the region and the cultural heritage of the region, taking into account the growing popularity of a healthy lifestyle, understanding the importance of good rest and recuperation;
- fuller and more efficient use of the healing, restorative and health-improving resources of the balneological resort of Sergiivka by introducing the work of modern SPA and Wellness complexes;
- reducing the man-made load on the environment, maintaining the status of an «environmentally friendly» resort;
- reduction of dependence on significantly worn out centralized power supply networks;
- introduction of alternative energy sources, resource-efficient technologies in the establishments of the hotel and restaurant and sanatorium-resort areas;
- reducing the use of synthetic materials, etc.

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